

On the expansion of training datasets to improve deep learning-based cell organelle recognition in fluorescence microscopy images of virus-infected cells

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Abstract: The Institute for Virology, Philipps-University, Marburg, developed a method to create image sequences of Marburg virus-infected live-cells. This work focuses on the expansion of image datasets by various transformation techniques to improve the training of a neural network for pattern recognition, i.e., the detection and classification of cell structures by means of pure green fluorescent imaging of subviral particles. The results show a high potential for automated segmentation of cell organelles.

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I. Introduction

Training neural networks (NN) to classify images requires huge amounts of data. This work deals with how to achieve good NN training results even with small datasets. Improving training with little amounts of data is important when creating or getting access to big amounts of data is either difficult or costly. Virologists of the Institute for Virology, Philipps-University, Marburg, developed a method to create image sequences of Marburg virus-infected live cells [1]. The image acquisition is a prime example of the costliness and complexity of gathering large datasets. Fluorescence microscopic image sequences of Marburg virus-infected cells form the basis of this work. The cell organelles and subviral particles can be labeled with fluorescent dye and are filmed in different color channels. While the red channel marks actin structures the blue channel highlights the nuclei of the cell. Subviral particles are visible in the green channel. We developed algorithms that automatically detect subviral particles in image sequences [2]. For this purpose, usually only the green channel is used. Still, information about cell morphology can be extracted from these images. Even though being a hard task for humans, this task can effectively be solved with a deep learning neuronal network approach, when sufficient training data is provided. This work focuses on the artificial expansion of the training dataset by applying different image transformations.

II. Material and methods

The NN used in this work is the convolutional NN Mask R-CNN, built in “TensorFlow” [3]. All additional code is written in Python using the “Spyder” framework.

II.I. Mask R-CNN

Mask R-CNN is not only able to locate and classify certain objects in an image, but it can also predict their shape and mark them with a mask. This NN consists of two stages each containing multiple layers.

The first stage creates a feature map containing information about which areas of the image have a high probability to contain objects. These proposed regions are then closely scanned and analyzed by the second stage. Finally, objects are classified, marked with a bounding box and overlaid by a mask indicating the shape of the object [4].

Mask R-CNN is trained on a dataset of images that are annotated with locations and shapes of objects in the image. The training data has been kindly provided by the Institute for Virology, Philipps-University, Marburg. Using different colorations to visualize cell structures, a lot of information about shapes and arrangements of cell structures in the image can be obtained. The information, previously validated by virologists, can be used to create manual annotations for each image.

II.II. Transformation strategies

By sufficiently transforming images, they can represent different or nearly new input data to a NN. To enhance the diversity of the initial dataset which consists of 10 images, four different transformation methods are used.

Adding noise to images is the first augmentation method used in this project. By superimposing each image with random noise, a purposefully changed image is created. This kind of augmentation is useful because the NN can learn to detect objects even if a noisy image is presented.

By rotating the image Mask R-CNN learns to detect objects independent of viewing angle. Rotating the image by any other angle than 90° , 180° and 270° causes parts of the image to get cut off by the image border. Because of this, images rotated by other angles must be zoomed out to provide extra space. This zooming out is an augmentation strategy by itself because it resizes objects in the image. Image shearing is applied in X and Y direction of the image, causing the shapes of object to be changed. Like rotating, this process can also cut off objects, creating the need to zoom out. The last transformation used in this work is the translation of the images. To be able to translate the images in all directions, the images must be zoomed out in the same way as in rotation and shearing. It is very important that the existing manual annotations of the images get transformed in the same way as the images themselves. Otherwise, the annotations would not line up with the actual objects in the image after transforming. Utilizing these augmentation strategies, a dataset of 860 training-images has been created by using only 10 base images.

Figure 1: Microscopic image marked with bounding boxes/masks showing the prediction of shape and location of cells, nuclei, and inclusions. Every bounding box is numerated in its top left corner. a) This image shows the predictions made by the NN trained with the base dataset of 10 images. Numbers 1-5 are labeling cells. Number 6 is marks an inclusion. b) This image shows the predictions made by the NN trained with the expanded dataset of 860 images. Number 1 to 6 are Cells; Numbers 7-10 are nuclei; And numbers 11 and 12 mark inclusions.

III. Results and discussion

In Fig. 1 the results of the Mask R-CNN object detection when used on an unclassified microscopic image of an infected cells are shown. The input image only provides the green channel, thus only containing information about the pictured subviral particles. Fig. 1 a) shows the estimated pre-dictions for cell organelle positions and shapes made by the NN trained on the base dataset. All cells have been success-fully classified. Zero out of 5 nuclei have been detected. One inclusion has been marked. Some masks, like 2, and 3 are not completely covering the area of the cell, leaving edges or corners out. Fig 1. b) shows the results obtained by the NN trained on the augmented dataset. Using only the subviral particles local distribution, all cells, and four out of five nuclei have been successfully classified and marked with a mask. Additionally, two clusters of subviral-particle-inclusions are highlighted. As in Fig 1. a) masks 4 and 6 do not cover the object completely.

Even though the classification and masks are not working perfectly yet, the obtained results using the expanded dataset are a good improvement compared to the results obtained without transformed images. This can especially be seen by the detection of nuclei. There is no doubt that the dataset expansion has improved the detection-accuracy. Nevertheless, the way the dataset is artificially expanded can still be upgraded by adding more transformations. Another useful augmentation strategy could be to select a certain amount of subviral particles, reducing the density of anchor points the NN can use.

IV. Conclusions

Several data augmentation strategies for enhancing small datasets for NN-training have been used in this work. The results show that the applied transformations are suitable to increase the size of small image-datasets. This information is of high value because being able to work with smaller datasets allows researchers to save time. Considering the cost and time required to create chemically colored microscopic images of cell infected with viruses supports this finding even more.

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